

How To Understand and Reduce Your Stress in Life

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Abstract— Human life is God's gift to all of us. We all want to be happy in life. However, life is not only about happiness but also stress at times. So stress is a part of our life. Every one of us has to face stress at times. This stress affects our body and mind very much. Stress cannot be completely eliminated but some ways to reduce stress can be managed. We can reduce stress by controlling our negative emotions. In this research paper deals with detail about what is stress, how to understand your stress, the effects of stress, the symptoms of stress in the body and mind. This research article also clearly explains some of the effective ways to help reduce stress.

Key words: Stress, Negative emotions, Positive emotions, Self- Care.

I. INTRODUCTION

From small challenges to major crises, stress has become a part of life today. When stress becomes too much or chronic it can seriously affect our lives. That is why it is so important to practice stress relievers that can calm our body and mind. Various factors influence the development of stress. In today's competitive world, competitive spirit, financial problems, love, lack of necessary facilities, non-availability of desired education, unemployment, low salary are all important factors in creating stress. So it is very important to identify the factors that cause our stress in our life and reduce them otherwise we may face various problems due to our stress.

II. OBJECTIVES

- To understand the stress and effect of stress.
- To know the physical and mental symptoms of stress.
- Effective ways to reduce your stress in life.

III. STRESS

Stress can be defined as a state of worry or mental tension caused by a difficult situation. Stress is a natural human response that prompts us to address. Stress is a feeling of emotional or physical tension. It can come from any event or thought that makes you feel frustrated, angry, or nervous. Everyone reacts differently to stressful situations. Coping styles and symptoms vary. Learning how to cope with stress can help our mental and physical well-being.

III.I. UNDERSTAND YOUR STRESS

The first step to reducing stress is to understand what is causing the stress. Stress triggers vary from person to person. So identifying the stressors is very important. Only then can steps be taken to reduce or avoid stress. Some common stressors include unemployment, Lack of finances, Breakdowns in relationships, Health problems, moving to a new place, Problems at work, Changes in life, Meeting a new person.

Finding the leading stress factors in your life is the first step toward effective stress management. Here are some common causes of stress: Work-related pressures, Financial difficulties, Relationship issues, Conflict with friends, family, or colleagues, Major life events and new changes.

III.II. EFFECTS OF STRESS

Poor health and illness. Chest pain, back pain, dizziness, headache, difficulty breathing, inability to sleep, abdominal pain and lack of energy. These are the most common reasons people consult a physician. Long-term ongoing stress can increase the risk for hypertension, heart attack, or stroke.

Symptoms of stress can affect your body, mind, and behavior. Unmanaged stress can lead to health problems like high blood pressure, heart disease, diabetes, and weight gain. Stress becomes a problem when it lasts for a long time or when you are unable to deal with it.

III.III. PHYSICAL AND MENTAL SYMPTOMS OF STRESS

When the mind is affected, it also affects the body. Some common body symptoms of stress include muscle tension, body fatigue, difficulty sleeping, eye irritation, vomiting, loss of appetite, fainting. Stress can cause mental anxiety, depression, irritability, difficulty concentrating, forgetfulness, and lack of understanding. Stress can also affect our behavior. Excessive stress lead to

addiction to unhealthy ways like drinking alcohol, smoking, drug addiction and making friends with the wrong friends. This kind of behavior affects our health greatly and this habit affects us and our family, our friends and our surroundings.

IV. EFFECTIVE WAYS TO REDUCE YOUR STRESS

IV.I. PRE-PLANNING

Planning is essential before taking any action. Proper planning will bring success in the activities undertaken. When we undertake an action without planning we are subjected to many disturbances and get stressed. For example when starting a new trip proper planning before starting the trip can avoid problem during the trip. A planned activity can reduce unnecessary tension and stress.

IV.II. REDUCE NEGATIVE EMOTIONS

Anger, fear, jealousy, fear, pride, and revenge are negative emotions .We cannot live without negative emotions. We can live interestingly in our life only if we have few negative emotions. Not only humans but also animals are prone to exhibit negative emotions. But when these negative emotions get out of control, we experience stress. When negative emotions are high, our body and mind are greatly affected. So learn to reduce negative emotions and cultivate positive emotions in any situation.

IV.III. TIME MANAGEMENT

Poor time management can lead to stress and anxiety. Time management is a very important skill to get our jobs done properly. Time management is the process of planning how to allocate and organize time for specific activities. Time management allows you to get more work done in less time. Able to plan and complete activities within specified. Procrastination can be avoided. We can avoid stress by completing specific task at specific time. By practicing time management we can reduce our stress.

IV.IV. DEVELOP A POSITIVE SELF-TALK HABIT

Always develop the habit of speaking positively. There should never be inferiority complex, harsh self-criticism, self-doubt, lack of self-confidence. If we keep thinking things like I can't stand it, I can't do anything right, and I don't have time for this, we stress ourselves out. So self-confidence is always very important. Avoid negative thoughts in any situation. Always have positive self-criticism. And while interacting with others we should have a trusting compassionate dialogue which will lead others and ourselves in a positive way.

IV.V. HOBBIES

Engaging in hobbies such as painting, reading, or playing music can help reduce stress and promote relaxation. Hobbies can provide a sense of accomplishment and help you take your mind off your worries. Having a hobby is a great way to spend your spare time and unwind from your daily routine - whether this be photography or taking part in a particular sport. Spending time on activities that you enjoy can help improve your mental health and wellbeing.

IV.VI. EXERCISE

Exercise is one of the most effective activities for reducing stress. Physical activity releases endorphins, which are natural mood boosters. Regular exercise can help reduce stress, improve mood and boost self-esteem. Exercise helps keep the blood flowing smoothly and gives good physical and mental health. You can try different types of exercise, such as jogging, yoga, swimming, or cycling. Exercise is a fantastic stress reliever.

IV.VII. EAT HEALTHY FOOD

A healthy diet can help reduce stress and improve physical and mental health. Good physical and mental health can be achieved by eating a balanced diet that includes fruits, vegetables, whole grains and fiber proteins. Sometimes being physically healthy can save you from the problems you face in life and live with good mental health. It is best to avoid low quality food items.

IV.VIII. ADEQUATE SLEEP

Proper sleep time at night and wake up time in the morning should be followed for good mental health. Getting enough sleep is important for good physical and mental health. By giving the body adequate rest, the body and mind can function smoothly. 6 to 8 hours of sleep is essential for good physical and mental health. Lack of proper sleep is also an important factor in stress. When we are sleep deprived, our daily activities are interrupted and we become stressed.

IV.IX. MEDITATION

One of the important benefits of meditation is its ability to reduce stress. It restores the body to a calm state, helping the body repair itself and preventing new damage from the physical effects of stress. There are many benefits to meditation, both mentally and physically. People with physical limitations may find it easier to practice than strenuous physical exercise for stress relief. Plus, no special equipment is required. Meditation is always available and can be done anywhere at any time. It is amazingly effective in short-term stress reduction and long-term health. The benefits of meditation can be felt in just one session.

IV.X. FOCUS ON BREATHING

Just focusing on your breath or changing the way you breathe can make a big difference to your overall stress level. Breathing techniques can calm your body and your brain in just a few minutes. Breathing exercises don't have to take a lot of time out of your day. Begin with just 5 minutes a day, and increase your time as the exercise becomes easier and more comfortable. If 5 minutes feels too long, start with just 2 minutes.

V. CONCLUSION

Uncontrolled stress can lead to serious illness and damage the body and mind. Coping with stress is all about identifying the causes of stress and trying to reduce them. Many factors contribute to stress. There are a variety of effective ways to reduce stress. Among them, planning ahead before doing any activity, exercising, yoga, meditation, nutritious food, adequate sleep, following punctuality, cultivating positive thoughts, performing positive actions, breathing exercises are methods to reduce stress. Stress can be reduced by reducing negative emotions and increasing positive emotions. Sometimes it is best to seek help from a doctor if the stress is unmanageable. Self-care is a great way to reduce stress.

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